

An automated approach to extracting positive and negative clinical research results

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Abstract

Failures are common in clinical trials, and these “successful” failures presented in negative results always reveal the paths that should not be pursued. In this study, we propose an automated method for extracting positive and negative clinical research outcomes using a ICOE (Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Effect) framework to represent randomized controlled trial (RCT) reports, with E denoting the effect between a specific Intervention and Outcome. We developed a pipeline for extracting and assigning the relevant statistical effect to a specific Intervention-Outcome pair from natural language RCT reports. The extraction models achieved high accuracy in extracting Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Effect descriptors through two rounds of training. By setting a p-value threshold, we found that negative results constituted nearly 40% of all Covid-19 related Intervention-Outcome pairs with statistical tests. We believe that this observation is noteworthy since they are extracted from the published literature, in which there is an inherent risk of reporting bias, preferring to report positive results over negative results. We have developed a tool that enables systematic understanding of the current level of clinical evidence by distinguishing between positive and negative results.

Introduction

Failure in science is an under-investigated area, although it is common especially in clinical trials (Yin et al., 2019). According to the new evidence-based medicine pyramid (Murad et al., 2016), randomized controlled trials (RCTs) are at the highest level while systematic reviews only play the role of lens inspecting all types of evidence. In other words, RCTs have the most reliable and straightforward conclusions when it comes to medical evidence appraisal. The results of RCTs are reported either in scientific publications or on registration platforms. Publication bias in RCTs is a noteworthy phenomenon that clinical researchers tend to publish statistically significant results over findings with no difference between the study groups (Easterbrook et al., 1991), and it has been causing time waste and false conclusions in the scientific community (Mlinarić et al., 2017). The discussions about failed and negative results have been gradually growing. Researchers proposed that negative results should be cared equally as positive results, and it is critical to publish all clinical trial studies regardless of the outcome (Nghiem et al., 2022). In the area of cancer disease, negative trials contribute similar-sized scientific impact as positive trials, generating important observations on what new treatments should be avoided (Unger et al., 2016). Besides, questions to ask when a primary outcome fails were also discussed by researchers (Pocock & Stone, 2016), meaning failed outcomes can potentially have great values that should not be ignored. In other words, these are “successful” failures, since these negative results indicate the ways that should not be taken to treat cancer. It is a change of thinking from “to do what” to “not to do what”. Also, failures can contribute to help researchers and policy-makers justify new clinical researches. A systematic review of evidence including both successes and failures is often required in new applications for clinical trial fundings to ensure the study is justified (Sandercock, 2012).

While encouraging researchers to disseminate synthesized analysis over positive and negative results, it is imperative for clinical researchers to automatically collect existing unintegrated results and structure them into a computational format. By distinguishing negative results from the positive results, both clinical researchers and public health policy-makers can capture a whole picture on both the successful and failed scientific evidence for informing an unbalanced and unbiased decision-making.

The Food and Drug Administration Amendments Act (FDAAA) in 2007 started to demand the studies registered on Clinicaltrials.gov to report results within 12 months of trial completion (Becker et al., 2014). Meanwhile, abstracts in publications contain a huge number of results from RCTs. Compared to the structured and organized XML formatted results on the registration website, clinical trial results from peer-reviewed publications are represented in natural languages in abstract, which are strenuous for researchers to manually extract and curate. Trialstreamer (Marshall et al., 2020) is a database of over 800 thousand RCTs in a PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcome) format. It also has an extracted punchline sentence showing the results of each study. Limitations of Trialstreamer include 1) unmatched end-to-end I-O pairs, 2) non-standardized outcomes, and 3) lack of components representing positive and negative results, such as p-value, 95% CI (confidence interval) and other statistical effect size. In this study, we aim to solve the mentioned shortcomings by developing an integrated natural language processing (NLP) pipeline with named entity recognition (NER) and relation extraction (RE) from RCTs results and conclusions. The proposed method focuses on the extraction of the statistical effects of interventions on outcomes. It is expected to help researchers acquire computational clinical evidence by discovering both positive and negative findings for medical knowledge mining, clinical decision support, systematic review, etc.

Methods

As of now, NLP techniques are being applied in various aspects of medicine including unstructured electronic medical records processing, medical literature mining, sentiment analysis, etc. In terms of clinical trial information extraction, researchers has utilized NLP to finish tasks such as eligibility criteria extraction (Kang et al., 2017) (Yuan et al., 2019), cohort selection (Chen et al., 2019), and advance care planning identification (Lindvall et al., 2022), and more. In this study, we aim to leverage NLP methods to extract ICOE (Intervention, Comparator, Outcome, and Effect) from unstructured expressions from abstracts of clinical trials.

The two primary subtasks involve the refined extraction of Intervention-Comparator-Outcome-Effect (ICOE) relationships and the identification of connections between outcomes and their effectiveness. Conventional methods for named entity recognition and relation extraction often employ a pipeline approach, initially extracting all entities mentioned in an abstract and subsequently passing them to a relation extraction module (Lee Grace E, and, Sun Aixin 2019. Marshall IJ et al 2020. Nye BE et al 2021). However, this may result in extraneous background information being extracted alongside crucial data, potentially hindering subsequent in-depth analyses. Moreover, we assert that the effectiveness of each outcome is vital information. As such, this paper extends beyond the scope of ICO entities by concentrating on extracting effectiveness data and establishing its connection to the ICO entities.

These tasks may be viewed as instances of Sentence Classification combined with Named Entity Recognition (NER) and co-occurred-based relation extraction (RE), respectively. Motivated by observations concerning how results tend to be described in trial reports, we propose a new pattern-based ICOE extraction approach that firstly independently identifies sentences that describe interventions (I) and comparison (C) drug with grouping design, and extract I and C from the grouping design sentence. Secondly, identifying outcomes (O) and comparative effectiveness (E), then using the extracted information to discover their co-occurrence at the sentence level, and create a relationship between outcomes and comparative effectiveness.

Figure 1. Overview of the ICOE recognition process

The proposed extraction method is shown in Figure 2. By integrating the structural features of abstracts with the extraction of ICOE entities at the sentence level, the accuracy of the results is optimized. In RCT abstracts, certain key aspects tend to follow a nearly fixed pattern. The two most important sentences for extracting ICOE are the drug grouping design sentence and the outcome with comparative effectiveness sentence. The extract process in this paper proceeds as follows:

- 1) A sentence classification model is first trained to detect grouping design sentences in a trial. These sentences describe drugs and population designs, for example, “This was a multicenter randomized controlled study including 96 patients with COVID- 19 who were randomly assigned into a chloroquine (CQ) group and a favipiravir group.” Here, chloroquine (CQ) and favipiravir represent the Intervention (I) and Comparison (C) entities, respectively. The linguistic and textual features of such design sentences are evident, typically including the terms like "patients / participants / randomized / assigned / group / versus, etc.", as well as experimental protocol descriptions such as “drug, dose (mg), frequency (two times a day), duration (for 14 days), etc.” A Bayesian classifier is employed for sentence classification.
- 2) An IC drugs extraction model is trained to obtain I and C entities from the detected drug grouping design sentences. Many studies have considered C as a subset of I, which may result in inaccurate extraction even when relevant content is identified by the model. In this paper we used a span-based NER model (Li et al., 2019) to learn from annotation data. The I and C entities are then extracted by pinpointing their respective starting and ending points within a sentence.

- 3) Afterwards, an Outcome NER model is needed to obtain the outcome named entities. In an RCT abstract, the Outcome (O) named entity may appear multiple times, but our primary interest lies in the O mentioned in sentences where effects are compared. For instance, in the sentence “one patient (2.3%) in the favipiravir group and two patients (4.2%) in the CQ group died (p = 1.00)”, the word "died" represents the O entity. A custom NLP model is developed to extract the O entity at the abstract level. An NLP framework, spaCy3, is employed to train this custom model using annotated data.
- 4) After extracting the O entity, the subsequent step is to extract the effectiveness(E) of the experiment results within the same sentence. Typically, there are two ways to describe E in an RCT abstract: the first involves the use of statistical indicators, such as "rate ratio, 0.95; 95% CI, 0.81 to 1.11; P-value= 0.50"; the other involves a textual description, where authors frequently describe the effect of the outcome in natural language without any indicators, such as "significantly higher, not different between, failed to attain statistical significance etc". Consequently, we introduce two extraction methods for these approaches:
 - a. Statistical indicators: We categorize statistical indicators into two types and designed templates using regular expressions for accurate extraction. One type comprises indicators representing the probability of an outcome compared to a control group, such as hazard ratio (HR), odds ratio (OR), and relative risk (RR). These can typically be written in the following forms: rate ratio, 0.95; 95% CI, 0.81 to 1.11; P-value= 0.50. The template is: “INDICATOR NUM, NUM % CI NUM to NUM, P VALUE = NUM”. The second type of indicator is a condensed version of the first, consisting solely of the P-value, which directly compares the numerical differences in outcomes between the experimental and control groups. The template for the second type of indicator is: "P VALUE = NUM".
 - b. Effect Description words: Since there are numerous effect description words and it would be too time-consuming to construct extraction rules for all of them, we treat the effect description words extraction task as another specialized NER task. We use the same model as for O, but trained it with different annotated data.
- 5) Outcome NER and result description words NER models are trained to obtain both outcome entities and descriptive word entities. Additionally, a rule-based results indicator extraction method is designed for extracting effectiveness indicators. We establish a rule that if an outcome entity and a results indicator or descriptive words co-occur within a sentence, the sentence is considered a clinical outcome results description sentence.
- 6) The final step is to correlate O and E by using sentence-level co-occurrence relationships. If O and E co-occur in the same sentence, it is highly likely that E represents the effectiveness results of O.

Figure 2. Overview of the ICOE extraction method based on abstract patterns

Data

We collected 216 abstracts from COVID-19 RCT studies in the MEDLINE database. A medical expert created the annotation rules, and two researchers from the same medical college completed the annotation. We performed a cross-validation of the annotations, resolving any disputes. Four categories of entities were labeled in the abstracts: I, C, O, and E-Description words. We excluded E-indicators like "odds ratio," "95% CI," and "p-value" since they can be easily extracted using regular expressions. We divided the dataset into an 80% training set and a 20% testing set. RCT abstracts typically contain one intervention/comparison and multiple outcomes with corresponding comparison words. We counted the unique entities in each dataset, using the 216 annotated data points as our gold standard.

As 216 annotated data points were insufficient to train a reliable model, we gathered all COVID-19 RCT studies from the PubMed database. After excluding non-drug treatment studies, 836 studies remained. Instead of manual annotation, we semi-automatically generated labels in the larger dataset using the model's predictions, which was trained on the gold standard dataset. We performed a brief manual review of incorrect predictions. Table 1 displays the dataset's statistical results.

Table 1. Count of annotated data

	Gold standards	Semi-automatically generated data
RCT Abstracts	216	836
Labeled Sentence for classification	216	492
Labeled I/C entities	178	477
Labeled Outcome entities	613	1476
Labeled Compare word entities	47	171

Results

Performance of the extraction models

To evaluate the models, we employed a 5-fold cross-validation, dividing the data into five equal groups. During each model training and testing run, 4/5 of the data was used as the training set, and 1/5 as the test set. The performance on the test sets is reported in Table 2. The models' performance was assessed using different training data (Gold standards / Semi-automatically generated data) and various entities. For each model setting, we recorded the best evaluation among the five sets for cross-validation and averaged measures, using the F1 score as the primary evaluation metric.

Table 2. Models' F1 score in different training sets

	Gold standards	Semi-automatically generated data
I/C	0.866	0.905
O	0.835	0.932
E-Description words	0.701	0.814

The table indicates that the models achieve high accuracy in extracting ICO and E-Description words through two training rounds. Table 3 demonstrates a sample recognition result, showing an RCT abstract converted into a set of ICOE entities, including the correspondence between O and E. In the sample, I represents Favipiravir, C represents Standard care alone, and there are five outcomes, four of which correspond to E as a statistical indicator, and one corresponds to E as a textual description.

It is worth noting that typically, only one drug is tested in a paper, so the relationship between I and O is naturally formed in the output result. Therefore, ICOEs could be linked as a small knowledge graph, providing a foundation for future applications.

Table 3. Sample output for our ICOE extraction method

PMID : 34849615	I/C	O-E
<p>Efficacy of Early Treatment With Favipiravir on Disease Progression Among High-Risk Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): A Randomized, Open-Label Clinical Trial</p> <p>Chuan Huan Chuah ¹, Ting Soo Chow ¹, Chee Peng Hor ^{2, 3}, Joo Thye Cheng ⁴, Hong Bee Ker ⁵, Heng Gee Lee ⁶, Kok Soon Lee ⁷, Noridah Nordin ⁸, Tiang Kai Ng ⁹, Masliza Zaid ¹⁰, Nor Zaila Zaidan ¹¹, Suhaila Abdul Wahab ¹², Nurul Ashikin Adnan ¹³, Noorlina Nordin ¹⁴, Tze Yuan Tee ¹⁵, Su Min Ong ¹⁶, Suresh Kumar Chidambaram ¹⁷, Mahiran Mustafa ⁸, Malaysian Favipiravir Study Group</p> <p>Collaborators, Affiliations + expand PMID: 34849615 DOI: 10.1093/cid/ciab962</p> <p>Abstract</p> <p>Background: The role of favipiravir in preventing disease progression in coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) remains uncertain. We aimed to determine its effect in preventing disease progression from nonhypoxia to hypoxia among high-risk COVID-19 patients.</p> <p>Methods: This was an open-label, randomized clinical trial conducted at 14 public hospitals across Malaysia (February–July 2021) among 500 symptomatic, RT-PCR-confirmed COVID-19 patients, aged ≥50 years with ≥1 comorbidity, and hospitalized within first 7 days of illness. Patients were randomized 1:1 to favipiravir plus standard care or standard care alone. Favipiravir was administered at 1800 mg 2x/day on day 1 followed by 800 mg 2x/day until day 5. The primary endpoint was rate of clinical progression from nonhypoxia to hypoxia. Secondary outcomes included rates of mechanical ventilation, intensive care unit (ICU) admission, and in-hospital mortality.</p> <p>Results: Of 500 patients randomized (mean [SD] age, 62.5 [8.0] years; 258 women [51.6%]; 251 [50.2%] had COVID-19 pneumonia), 487 (97.4%) patients completed the trial. Clinical progression to hypoxia occurred in 46 (18.4%) patients on favipiravir plus standard care and 37 (14.8%) on standard care alone (OR, 1.30; 95% CI: .81–2.09; P = .28). All 3 prespecified secondary endpoints were similar between both groups. Mechanical ventilation occurred in 6 (2.4%) vs 5 (2.0%) (OR, 1.20; 95% CI: .36–4.23; P = .76). ICU admission in 13 (5.2%) vs 12 (4.8%) (OR, 1.09; 95% CI: .48–2.47; P = .84), and in-hospital mortality in 5 (2.0%) vs 0 (OR, 12.54; 95% CI: .76–207.84; P = .08) patients.</p>	<p>I: Favipiravir C: Standard care alone</p>	<p>O: Clinical progression to hypoxia E: odds ratio, 1.30; 95% CI: .81–2.09; P-value=.28</p>
	<p>O: Mechanical ventilation E: odds ratio, 1.20; 95% CI: .36–4.23; P-value=.76</p>	
	<p>O: ICU admission E: odds ratio, 1.09; 95% CI: .48–2.47; P-value=.84</p>	
	<p>O: risk of disease progression E: odds ratio, 12.54; 95% CI: .76–207.84; P-value=.08</p>	
	<p>O: disease progression E: not prevent</p>	

Positive versus negative results

We separately extracted P-values and analyzed the proportion of positive and negative results. We employed the conventional statistical P-value threshold of 0.05 to differentiate between positive and negative results. Results with P-value <0.05 indicate that the intervention group (I) has a significant difference in the outcome (O) compared to the comparison group (C). Conversely, results with P-value ≥ 0.05 suggest that the intervention group (I) shows no significant difference in the outcome (O) compared to the comparison group (C).

The language expressions for P-values differ across study results. The following table displays the count of each expression and the corresponding positive/negative mapping. Positive results account for 62% of all results, while 38% are negative. Table 4 presents the full statistics of positive and negative P-values with different operators.

Table 4. The statistics of positive and negative results by P-value

Operator	Count	Positive	Negative
Equal to (=)	777	417	360
Greater than (>)	31	0	31
Less than (<)	219	217	2

Greater than or equal to (\geq)	0	0	0
Less than or equal to (\leq)	8	8	0
Total	1035	642 (62.0%)	393 (38.0%)

Conclusions

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt to extract the statistical effects of specific intervention-outcome pairs from natural language RCT reports, where multiple measured outcomes are described in a single sentence. By setting a p-value threshold, we discovered that nearly 40% of all COVID-19-related intervention-outcome pairs with statistical tests had negative results. We believe that this observation is noteworthy, as it is based on published literature, in which there is an inherent risk of reporting bias that favors positive results over negative ones.

Medical bibliographic databases and clinical trial registries are the two primary sources of RCT reports. In contrast to the former, a registry like ClinicalTrials.gov contains over four hundred thousand structured and semi-structured trial records, as well as more than fifty-four thousand reported results. We estimate that incorporating results from ClinicalTrials.gov would likely increase the proportion of negative results. Our future work will involve identifying conflicting intervention-outcome pairs and analyzing the reasons behind them, such as varying conditions or sample sizes. Additionally, we will refine the definitions of positive and negative results beyond p-values by introducing other statistical indicators like "95% confidence intervals."

Through a critical scrutinization on what is known, clinical researchers can systematically understand the current level of scientific evidence. It is also in accordance with the idea of metaknowledge (i.e., knowledge on knowledge), which will enable researchers to reshape science—to identify areas in need of reexamination and reweight former certainties (Evans & Foster, 2011).

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